

Open Source Software Development Process: A Systematic Review

Automated Search Execution

Chosen Digital Libraries:

Digital Library	Link
Scopus	https://www.scopus.com/
IEEE Xplore	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp
ACM Digital Library	https://dl.acm.org/
Web of Science	https://apps.webofknowledge.com/

Adapted search query for each Digital Library:

- **Scopus** (Advanced search)
TITLE-ABS-KEY ("open source" OR "free source") AND ("software development process" OR "development process" OR "software process") AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "COMP"))

- **IEEE Xplore** (General search)
("open source" OR "free source") AND ("software development process" OR "development process" OR "software process")

- **ACM Digital Library** (Advanced search)
Title:((("open source" OR "free source") AND ("software development process" OR "development process" OR "software process")))

Abstract:((("open source" OR "free source") AND ("software development process" OR "development process" OR "software process")))

Keyword:((("open source" OR "free source") AND ("software development process" OR "development process" OR "software process")))

- **Web of Science** (Topic – searches title, abstract, author keywords and keywords plus)
("open source" OR "free source") AND ("software development process" OR "development process" OR "software process")

The searches were executed in October 2020. Results from each Digital Library and merged results:

Digital Library	Number of returned papers
Scopus	764
IEEE Xplore	358
ACM DL	127
Web of Science	472
Total:	1721
After removing conferences announcements and duplicated papers:	1229